

Title:

Compensation of the effect of scanning directions on magnetic force imaging

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Abstract

It was found that the results of magnetic force microscope (MFM) imaging were different with the probe scanning directions, and the images were often distorted. This paper studied the effect of scanning directions on the MFM imaging, and a method for the distortion compensation was proposed to reduce the errors. In the study, three different scanning directions with the angles of 0° , 45° and 90° , were used to measure the magnetic force distribution of a magnetic sample with a regular structure. The theoretical and experimental results have shown that the scanning direction parallel to the magnetic structure will cause a minimum phase shift difference and lead to a structure distortion. With the proposed compensation method, the distortion structures were corrected and the effect of scanning directions on the MFM imaging was significantly reduced. This work provides a way to obtain the correct images of magnetic structures using an MFM and to improve the imaging quality in a wide range of MFM applications.

Keywords: Magnetic Force Microscope (MFM); Distortion Compensation; Different Scanning Directions; Phase Shift Difference; Structure Distortion.

1. Introduction

Magnetic force microscopy has been developed for researching the precise characters of magnetic properties by a magnetic probe [1-3]. Because of the nanoscale resolution of MFM [4-6], it has been used as a powerful tool to observe the magnetic

microstructure distributions of various magnetic materials [7, 8] and manipulate the magnetic objects [9, 10]. Many reported studies have been focused on the improvement of the resolution of MFM images [11-13]. Winkler et. al. [14], Choi et. al. [15], Wolny et. al. [16] and Lisunova et. al. [17] developed a carbon nanotube on the conventional MFM tip to obtain high resolution MFM images. Nyamjav et. al., Huang et. al. [18] and Nenadovića et. al. [19] analyzed the quality of MFM images with various lift heights of magnetic probes and found that the lift height significantly affected the resolution of MFM images based on the natures of samples. Besides the lift height, the probe scanning directions also affected the quality of magnetic force imaging [20]. However, there has been no work reported to study the effect of scanning directions on MFM imaging.

In this work, a regular magnetic structure was used as a sample to provide a periodic pattern for MFM imaging. Three different scanning directions with the angles of 0° , 45° and 90° were used to measure the magnetic force distributions of the regular magnetic structure. A method for the distortion compensation was proposed to reduce the errors and structure distortion of MFM images. The results showed that the proposed compensation method was able to correct the distortions and significantly reduce the effect of scanning directions on the MFM imaging. The method is described in the following sections.

2. Methods and materials

A BENYUAN MFM system (CSPM 5500) was used for the measurement of magnetic domain distributions under ambient conditions. The resonant frequency of the magnetic probe was 75 kHz and the force constant was 3 N/m (MagneticMulti75-G, BudgetSensors). A nanometer pattern generation system (NPGS) (JC Nability NPGS V9.1) integrated together with the scanning electronic microscope (SEM) system (FEI QUANTA-250 FEG) was used for the generation of a regular magnetic structure. For the regular magnetic sample, the substrate is silicon and the magnetic material is the nickel film with a thickness of 100 nm on the substrate. The nickel film is covered by photoresist (nonmagnetic material) with a thickness of 200 nm.

3. Theory

To obtain the MFM images, two successive scans with a tapping mode were applied. The scanning mode can separate a long range force from a short range force [21, 22]. As shown in Figure 1, in the first scan, the probe was tapping at a resonant frequency and the topography was obtained. In the second scan, the probe was lifted several nanometers from the surface and traced the topography profile to obtain the magnetic force [23, 24].

Figure 1 Schematic diagram of an MFM imaging system.

The phase shift is measured for magnetic force imaging, which is proportional to the derivative of the tip-sample force in the z direction, and it can be calculated as [25]

$$\Delta\varphi = \varphi_R - \varphi_D = \frac{Q}{k} \frac{\partial F_z}{\partial z} \quad (1)$$

where φ_R is the reference phase shift from the reference signal $f_R(t)$ used for driving the piezo in a tapping mode. φ_D is the detected phase shift from the detected signal $f_D(t)$ obtained from the optical position sensitive detector (PSD). Q and k are the quality factor and spring constant of the cantilever, respectively. The gradient force can be given as [26]

$$\frac{\partial F_z}{\partial z} = M_{tip} \frac{\partial^2 B_z}{\partial z^2} \quad (2)$$

where the M_{tip} is the magnetic momentum of magnetic tip. For a magnetic sample with periodic structures, the magnetic field B_z can be computed as [27]

$$B_z = \sum_n B_n e^{-n\omega z} \sin(n\omega x + \delta_n) \quad (3)$$

where B_n depends on the magnetic field of magnetic sample and $\omega = 2\pi/T$. T is the structure period. (2) can be rewritten as

$$\frac{\partial F_z}{\partial z} = M_{tip} \sum_n (n\omega)^2 B_n e^{-n\omega z} \sin(n\omega x + \delta_n) \quad (4)$$

Thus, the expression for the phase shift is given by

$$\Delta\varphi = \sum_n A_n e^{-n\omega z} \sin(n\omega x + \delta_n) \quad (5)$$

where $A_n = \frac{Q}{k} M_{tip} (n\omega)^2 B_n$.

Figure 2(A) is the illustration of the regular magnetic sample structure. In the MFM imaging process, the three scanning directions 0° , 45° and 90° were used to image the magnetic sample, as shown in Figure 2(B). The scan direction parallel to the magnetic structure in the imaging is selected as the scanning direction of 0° . If the scan direction is vertical to the magnetic structure, the scanning direction is 90° . If the intersection angle between the scan direction and the magnetic structure is 45° , the scanning direction is 45° .

Figure 2 Illustration of imaging with different scanning directions on the magnetic sample. (A) is the structure of the regular magnetic sample, (B) shows the scanning angles between the scanning direction and magnetic structure 0° , 45° and 90° .

The phase shift differences are

$$\begin{aligned}\Delta\varphi_{0^\circ} &= \Delta\varphi_{OA} = \varphi_O - \varphi_A \\ \Delta\varphi_{45^\circ} &= \Delta\varphi_{OB} = \varphi_O - \varphi_B \\ \Delta\varphi_{90^\circ} &= \Delta\varphi_{OC} = \varphi_O - \varphi_C\end{aligned}\tag{6}$$

Substituting (6) into (5) and then the phase shift difference expressions are

$$\begin{aligned}\Delta\varphi_{0^\circ} &= Ae^{-\omega x} (\sin(\omega x + \delta_O) - \sin(\omega x + \delta_A)) \\ \Delta\varphi_{45^\circ} &= Ae^{-\omega x} (\sin(\omega x + \delta_O) - \sin(\omega x + \delta_B)) \\ \Delta\varphi_{90^\circ} &= Ae^{-\omega x} (\sin(\omega x + \delta_O) - \sin(\omega x + \delta_C))\end{aligned}\tag{7}$$

It is known that $\delta_A = \delta_O$, $\delta_B = \delta_O + 45^\circ$ and $\delta_C = \delta_O + 90^\circ$; and the phase shift differences can be expressed as

$$\begin{aligned}\Delta\varphi_{0^\circ} &= 0 \\ \Delta\varphi_{45^\circ} &= Ae^{-\omega x} \left(\frac{2 - \sqrt{2}}{2} \sin(\omega x + \delta_O) - \frac{\sqrt{2}}{2} \cos(\omega x + \delta_O) \right) \\ \Delta\varphi_{90^\circ} &= Ae^{-\omega x} (\sin(\omega x + \delta_O) - \cos(\omega x + \delta_O))\end{aligned}\tag{8}$$

When the angle between the scanning direction and the magnetic structure is 0° , the phase shift difference is 0° . Accordingly, the structures parallel to the scanning direction are imaged with distortions. To correct the phase shift signal obtained by the scanning direction of 0° , an MFM imaging compensation method was proposed, expressed by (9). The software Matlab was used to simulate the expression. The simulation result is shown in Figure 3. Figure 3(B) is the enlarged image of the square area in Figure 3(A). Here, $\omega x + \delta_O$ is assumed to be θ and ranged from 0° to 2π . It can be seen that the phase shift difference is significantly influenced by the scanning direction. The minimum phase shift difference (red line) is obtained with the scanning

direction of 0° and its ideal value is 0° , leading to a structure distortion. It is known from Figure 3(A) that with the proposed compensation MFM imaging method, the phase shift differences obtained by the scanning directions of 90° and 45° are mostly failed to compensate the results acquired with the scanning direction of 0° . Figure 3(B) shows that the compensated phase shift differences (black line) cannot always be compensated by the values of 90° and 45° phase shift differences. The dashed line b-1 shows the results of the scanning directions of 90° and 45° compensated for 0° . The dash line b-2 shows that the phase shift differences of the scanning direction of 45° are failed to compensate the errors and the result values are higher than the phase shift differences obtained with the scanning directions of 90° and 0° . The phase shift differences with the 90° scanning direction are compensated for the results of 45° and 0° , as shown in the dashed line b-3. It can be concluded that the compensation method of MFM imaging corrects the distortion structures and improves the imaging accuracy. The MFM imaging compensation method can be described as

$$\Delta\varphi_{Compensation} = \frac{1}{3} (\Delta\varphi_{0^\circ} + \Delta\varphi_{45^\circ} + \Delta\varphi_{90^\circ}) \quad (9)$$

Figure 3 Phase shift differences with three different scanning directions. (B) is the enlarged image of the square area in (A).

4. Result and discussion

In order to study the effect of scanning directions on the quality of MFM imaging, the MFM images of floppy and hard disks scanned with 0° , 45° and 90° are presented. Figures 4(A-C) show the MFM images of a floppy disk scanned with different scanning directions, and the lift height is 70 nm. Figures 4(E-G) show the MFM images of a hard disk imaged with different scanning directions at a lift height of 50 nm. It can be seen that the features of MFM images with the scanning direction of 0° is not visible in Figure 4(A) and the magnetic domain structures are indistinct in Figure 4(E). While those visible periodic magnetic domain structures are clearly recognized with the scanning directions of 45° and 90° , as shown in Figures 4(B-C) and (F-G).

Figure 4(D) shows the profiles of the floppy disk MFM images with three different scanning directions. The phase shift profile of the MFM image with the scanning direction parallel to the magnetic domains has small variations, ranged from 0.58° to 0.66° . However, the phase shift profile of the MFM image scanned with the direction of 45° is varied from 0.33° to 0.87° and that with the direction of 90° is ranged from 0.34° to 0.87° . The cross-sectional curves of the hard disk MFM images with three different scanning directions are shown in Figure 4(H). The phase shift acquired with the scanning direction of 0° is ranged from 0.22° to 0.32° . The phase shift of magnetic domain structures imaged with the scanning direction of 45° is varied from 0.04° to 0.45° and that with the scanning direction of 90° is varied from 0.03° to 0.45° .

It can be concluded from Figure 4 that the scanning directions have significant effects on the magnetic structure imaging. Especially for the MFM images which have the scanning directions parallel to the magnetic structures, there are distortions for the magnetic features.

Figure 4 MFM images of floppy and hard disks. (A) Floppy disk MFM image scanned with the scanning direction of 0° , (B) image with the scanning direction of 45° , and (C) image with the scanning direction of 90° . (D) The profile curves extracted from (A), (B) and (C). (E) Hard disk MFM image with the scanning direction of 0° , (F) with the scanning direction of 45° , and (G) with the scanning direction of 90° . (H) The cross-sectional curves of (E), (F) and (G).

To estimate the proposed distortion compensation method, a regular magnetic structure with four different directions was obtained by NPGS system. Figure 5 shows the SEM images and MFM topography images of the regular magnetic sample used for MFM imaging.

Figure 5 Images of the regular magnetic sample. (A) is the SEM image and (B) is the MFM topography image.

Figure 6 shows the MFM images of the regular magnetic sample with three scanning directions. The four direction magnetic structures are obtained with the scanning directions of 0° , 45° and 90° . The compensated MFM images of Figures 6(A-C) are shown in Figure 6(D). The cross-sectional curves of the phase shifts extracted from Figure 6 are shown in Figure 7.

The phase shifts of A-1, B-1, C-1 and D-1 in Figure 6 are shown in Figure 7(A). The phase shift obtained with the scanning direction of 0° is ranged from 0.089° to 0.115° and the compensated phase shift is varied from 0.086° to 0.123° . The phase shifts of A-2, B-2, C-2 and D-2 in Figure 6 are shown in Figure 7(B). The phase shift obtained with the scanning direction of 0° is ranged from 0.091° to 0.145° and the compensated phase shift is varied from 0.088° to 0.143° . The phase shifts of A-3, B-3, C-3 and D-3 in Figure 6 are shown in Figure 7(C). The phase shift obtained with the scanning direction of 0° is ranged from 0.08° to 0.116° and the compensated phase shift is varied from 0.079° to 0.127° . It is known that the difference value of the compensated phase shift is higher than the contrast value of the phase shift obtained

with the scanning direction of 0° . It can be seen from Figure 6 that the bottom-right structures in area I, the top-left structures in area II and the bottom-left structures in area III are the highest distortions compared with the structures in other directions. However, the structures of each direction are clearly shown after the compensation processed, as shown in Figure 6(D).

Consequently, it has proved that the scanning direction parallel to the magnetic structure leads to a distortion of the structure, and its phase shift difference is declined. It can be concluded that with the MFM imaging compensation method, the distortion structures can be corrected and the effect of scanning directions on the MFM imaging is significantly reduced.

Figure 6 MFM images of the regular magnetic sample with different scanning directions. (A) with the scanning direction of 0° , (B) with the scanning direction of 45° and (C) with the scanning direction of 90° . (D) Compensation result. The arrow shows the scanning directions. The scale of the range is in micron (μm) and the lift height is 45 nm.

Figure 7 Cross-sectional curves of phase shifts obtained with the three different scanning directions and compensation.

5. Conclusion

In the work, the effect of scanning directions on the magnetic imaging was investigated. It can be concluded from the theoretical and experimental results that the scanning direction of magnetic probe parallel to the magnetic structure can cause a minimum phase shift difference and lead to a distortion of the scanned structure. The phase shift difference was large when the scanning direction was vertical to the magnetic structure. The MFM imaging compensation method was developed to improve the accuracy of magnetic structure distribution measurement. With the proposed compensation method, the distortion structures were corrected and the effect of scanning directions on the MFM imaging was significantly reduced. This work provides a way to obtain the correct images of magnetic surface structures using MFM and to improve the imaging quality in a wide range of MFM applications.

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Declaration of interest

The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

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